

D1.1 Benchmarking R&I Strategies and Priorities for a Joint Una Europa Strategy

Una.Resin Project Deliverable D1.1

Final Version

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Abbreviations

Una Europa Member Universities

FUB	Freie Universität Berlin
KU Leuven	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
LEI	Universiteit Leiden
UCM	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
UEDIN	The University of Edinburgh
UH	Helsingin Yliopisto
UJ	Uniwersytet Jagiellonski
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
UP1	Université Paris I Pantheon- Sorbonne

Other Abbreviations

EASSH	European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities
EUA	European University Association
GA	Grant Agreement
LERU	League of European Research Universities
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
OH	One Health
PSC	Project Steering Committee
R&I	Research and Innovation
RCC	Una.Resin Research Coordination Cluster (research professionals representing each Una Europa university)
RIC	Research Infrastructure Cluster (research professionals representing each Una Europa university)
RIR	Research Infrastructures and Resource
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SSC	Self-Steering Committee (academic leads of a Una Europa focus area)
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
TMO	Time Machine Organisation
WP1	Work Package 1: Una Europa Research & Innovation
WP2	Work Package 2: Una Europa Infrastructure & Resources
WP3	Work Package 3: Una Europa Strengthening Human Capital

1. Introduction

Una.Resin work package 1 (WP1) “Una Europa Research & Innovation” is led by the University of Helsinki (UH) and co-lead by the Freie Universität Berlin (FUB). According to the Grant Agreement (GA) 101017416-Una.Resin, the objectives of WP1 are the following:

1. To create a long-term Una Europa research and innovation strategy and roadmap towards converging strengths, scaling excellence, and reinforcing impact by addressing a set of priority challenges on a European and global level.
2. To develop a systematic approach to engendering and supporting cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaborations and networks, in particular between SSH and STEM fields, to build capacity to address the priority challenges.
3. To converge policies and guidelines for implementing and mainstreaming Open Science to ensure access and impact of research and to enable wide-ranging collaboration in addressing the strategically chosen challenges.
4. To develop, implement and evaluate pilot actions for creating cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral teams across Una Europa.
5. To collect and analyse findings, make recommendations, contribute to final combined project recommendation paper.

The purpose of this report is to present the empirical base for objective 1, the Una.Resin Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy, gathered through various activities. Each chapter is dedicated to a specific benchmarking or consultation exercise which varies in scope, methodology, and target group. In addition to presenting the results of task 1.1 “Benchmarking Una Europa member universities’ R&I strategies,” as well as reflections on defining priority challenges (task 1.4), the report also entails the results of task 1.5 “Interactive online consultation with the UNA Europa community.” In the conclusion, we provide a synthesis of topics and tools which can serve as building blocks for the Una Europa R&I strategy.

Note: Being aware of the differences between cross-, multi-, trans-, and interdisciplinary research, the use of one term in this report is not meant to be suggestive. We recommend that Una Europa should embrace and support all ways of broadening research perspectives. Decisions on exact approaches have to be taken by the researchers from the bottom-up.

2. R&I Strategy Benchmarking

2.1. Methodology

2.1.1. Sources

As part of the Una Europa R&I strategy preparation, WP1 conducted a benchmarking of Una Europa universities' R&I strategies and policies. The analysis included both strategic research areas as well as policies and practices of each university. The aim was to identify areas of convergence, complementary strengths as well as common strategic aims. The results have provided a deeper understanding of the policies of the eight partners universities and will serve as a foundation for the future Una.Resin strategy process, including the design of pilot actions.

Three sources were consulted for the analysis:

1. Benchmarking questionnaire (see Annex A)
2. Una.Resin GA Annex 1 - Description of Action (part B): Descriptions of the consortium partners
3. Publicly available information on the institutions' websites (see Annex B)

WP1 designed the questionnaire jointly with Una.Resin WP2 (Sharing of Infrastructures) in order to align the mapping of research policies with that of policies on research infrastructures. As both questionnaires were potentially targeted at the same research service professionals of all eight Una Europa partners, the alignment avoided parallel inquiries and facilitated a lean process.

In the preparation stage, a first draft questionnaire in English was presented to Una.Resin PSC members for feedback. Subsequently, the questionnaire was sent to the members of the Una.Resin Research Coordination Cluster (RCC) and the Research Infrastructure cluster (RIC), who were briefed about the aims of the benchmarking exercise in an on-line session. The process of collecting the data for the questionnaire was left to the individual institutions. The final WP2 questionnaire consisted of the following sections:

Part 1: R&I strategies and strategic initiatives (WP1)

Part 2: Research infrastructure and resources (RIRs) (WP2)

While all universities returned the questionnaire, the answers varied greatly in scope, detail, and focus. Reasons for this could be the openness of the questions, the limited capacities of university administrations to gather more information, the unclear responsibilities and/or the need to consult across administrative units, as well as language barriers. Consequently, in addition to the questionnaire, we extended our analysis to the Una.Resin grant agreement as well as to the universities' websites in order to identify research priorities on an institutional level.¹

We limited the scope to strategies formulated at the main university level. Strategies of individual faculties, departments, or units, if existing, were not considered in this analysis.

¹ Initial plans to analyse additional data such as strategies of individual departments or bibliometrics could not be completed due to capacity constraints within WP1. The complexity of carrying out benchmarking exercises at eight institutions and the required preparation and work load need to be considered in the future.

2.1.2. Analysis

This report analyses “Part 1: R&I strategies and strategic initiatives (WP1)” of the questionnaire which contained ten questions with sub-questions addressing following topics: R&I strategies, research themes, funding, fields of excellence, multidisciplinary structures, multidisciplinary research, partnerships, regional focus areas, collaboration with Una partners, and research ethics (Annex A). In analysis we prioritised those questions relevant for the strategic choices to be made by the Una Europa general assembly in June 2022.

None of the Una Europa universities had strategy documents on hand which exclusively concerned research and innovation. However, seven of the eight universities had mapped out strategies that included strategic goals for research or had communications that conveyed research policies, guiding principles and/or institutional values. In order to map these values and put them in relation to one another, we analysed the strategic aims and values described in the questionnaire (question 1 on existing or planned multi-annual research strategies) as well as the documents provided on the university web pages with Atlas.ti, a research analysis software for qualitative data analysis and mixed methods. After an initial screening of the data, we devised three guiding questions according to our project goals (for the Atlas.si outcomes, see Annex C):

1. What kind of intentions can be derived from the responses the partners provided?
2. What values and strategic choices are reflected in already existing strategies?
3. What is their relation to each other?

Other topics in the questionnaire, namely questions 2, 4, 5, 7, 8 and 9, were processed in MS Excel and arranged into categorized tables. For questions 2, 4 and 5 (referring to research areas, themes or fields) two different analyses were conducted:

1. Categorisation according to 1Europe focus areas: We assumed that a connection between education and research within Una Europa activities was strategically relevant. Responses were thus grouped within a category of a 1Europe focus area if suitable. The remaining content was arranged into other research area-, theme-, or field-related categories.
2. Analysis without defined categorization: For all other questions, we derived the categorization from the responses given.

In the following, we present key outcomes and remarks. The analysis is not comprehensive and provides a snapshot of dynamic and complex institutional frameworks. The raw data presented as analysis excels will be available for future use on the Una Europa common data storage platform once such is in place. In the later stages of the project, we will re-visit the questionnaire outcomes as needed and share the data with other Una Europa strategy development teams. For instance, the benchmarking questionnaire asked for strategies with a geographical focus as well as international partnerships. This data can provide insights for the Una International Strategy development.

2.2. Results

2.2.1. Strategic Goals at a University Level

Una Europa partners are large universities of high research activity which partially differ in scope. Some institutions for example, include a school of engineering, whereas others are more strongly orientated towards social sciences and humanities. Yet, all Una Europa universities host multiple disciplines and operate under the premise of academic freedom. They build on practices that aim to nurture excellence and competitive bottom-up funding. Individual faculties, departments and chairs are responsible for research and defining priorities. Depending on the institution, faculty choices can be aligned with those of the university’s leadership.

Excellence was undeniably a prime goal of all universities, even though the exact meaning of this term remains elusive. Generally, it was stressed that excellence in research allows impact on a global scale. Excellence was also linked to innovative research and high standards in education and thus directly linked to the reputation of the institution depicted as an attractive and desirable place to research and study. Some of the universities declared to be future-orientated, brave and radical by virtue of investing in emerging research fields.

As expected, most universities stated that they did not formulate strategic or thematic priorities. Rather, research priorities were bottom-up and excellence driven. Indeed, all Una Europa members highlighted a **bottom-up curiosity-based approach to research**. All universities express their commitment to enhance **interdisciplinarity**, a goal often stated as a way to increase excellence. Some institutions regarded interdisciplinary structures as foundational building blocks for fields of excellence.

Unsurprisingly, Una Europa universities were all guided by similar values and principles. All universities articulated a strong commitment to **academic freedom, ethics, truth, integrity, and inclusivity**. Definitions of these terms were mostly not provided but assumed to be universally understood.

Openness, in general, was associated with science communication, supporting democracy through research, citizen science involving the local community, and interactions with policy makers. Interactions with non-academic partners was not seen as unidirectional—a university catalysing society—but rather as potential source of inspiration for research initiatives relevant to society. Openness was also seen as a catalyst for business and industry collaboration, offers in continuous learning as another way to engage broader society. (Note: A detailed analysis of open science policies was conducted separately within Una.Resin).

All universities aimed to **innovate**, but what kind of innovations were pursued were often not explained further. Three of the Una universities were more explicitly directed towards technological innovation, technology transfers and commercialization (KU Leuven, UNIBO and UEDIN) than the others.

All universities emphasized the importance of **international collaboration** in their strategies or principles. Measures advocated to increase collaboration, encourage researchers to participate in international networks and mobility schemes, provide funding and promote international regulatory frameworks for scientific research. Five of the universities also declared **collaboration on a local level** as a strategic goal or describe collaboration with local actors as essential.

Most Una Europa universities also included **work culture and professional development** of academics and professional staff in their strategic goals as well as the quality of the governance and management. Some universities also considered improving management processes as an essential tool for increasing excellence and the impact of education and research.

Sustainability and the United Nations 2030 Agenda were widely accepted strategic aims for all Una Europa universities and all universities aimed to solve big societal challenges.

2.2.2. Strategic Research Areas

In the questionnaire, we asked for defined strategic research themes or areas on all-university levels. In general, Una Europa universities were bottom-up, excellence driven and did not hierarchically rank their strategic areas. Instead, academic freedom as well as success in competitive funding calls defined the directions of research.

The analysis of the representation on the institutional websites as well as the responses to the WP1 questionnaire reveal that certain priorities do exist. Six out of eight universities listed several university-wide strategic themes or key areas. These strategic or key areas were mainly broad multidisciplinary themes and considered as “inspirational”. The main purposes of such defined areas were to:

- Communicate the strengths of the university
- Foster cross-departmental interdisciplinarity

- Enhance research excellence, inspire new directions in research and teaching, also in connection to major societal challenges
- Position the universities well in competitive national and international funding calls

While Una Europa universities did not dedicate specific funding to strategic areas (unless indirectly via RIRs) the areas often served to showcase excellence or the existence of multidisciplinary approaches vis-a-vis certain initiatives or funding agencies. In some cases, the reverse was true: research initiatives on national level motivated the articulation and funding of certain strategic or multidisciplinary research areas. National or internal funding instruments helped build strategic capacities such as areas of excellence, multidisciplinary units for emerging areas, local specialization, and research transfer. Nonetheless, Una Europa universities emphasized that national or regional policies did not impact their agenda setting in any major way.

We also asked to provide information on how the strategic areas were chosen: methods used to identify strategic areas varied and included tools such as systematic SWOT analyses, collaborative workshops with various stakeholders, and discussions among researchers. Other criteria that guided the selection was the existence of a high number of researchers working in these areas as well as priorities articulated by funding agencies. Strategic collaborations including Una Europa were also mentioned as a criterion.

Below we have provided a list of the strategic research areas indicated in the questionnaire. Due to the different levels on which these areas are formulated, we have listed them according to university rather than theme. However, grouped into clusters, it is evident that existing Una Europa focus areas overlap with the research commitment of many Una Europa partners. Seven out of eight universities named research areas linked to One Health, seven universities named sustainability or related concepts as a key area, five universities listed cultural heritage as well as AI. Areas related to society and the economy were also named by five institutions. Only two universities named areas linked to the emerging focus area that deals with new materials.

Research Areas listed by the Una Europa universities as strategic or as key areas:

- **UEDIN:** Five university-level themes aim to foster cross-faculty interdisciplinarity research: **culture & creativity; this digital life; One Health; the future of health & care; futureproofing societies & the planet.**
- **UH:** During the UH strategy period 2021-2030, research and teaching will draw inspiration from four themes that will spur collaboration between different disciplines and inspire research and teaching that seek solutions to major global problems: **a meaningful life, human wellbeing, and a healthy environment; a humane and fair world; a sustainable and viable future for our globe; a universe of ideas and opportunities**
- **UNIBO's** Strategic Plan underlines 8 strategic areas. These areas are broad, highly interdisciplinary, and strictly related to the SDGs: **industry 4.0, health and wellness, agro-food, big data and AI, art and human sciences in the digital age, interculturality, inclusion and social security, climate change, sustainability and circular economy.**
- **UCM** has no specific strategic areas or research themes. However, there are four major areas distributed across the 26 faculties: **experimental, health, humanities, and social sciences.**
- **FUB** does not have any current strategic focus areas. During the so-called Excellence Initiative (2007-2019), FUB maintained five so-called Focus Areas. Of these, only the **Dahlem Humanities Center** has continued as a permanent institution.
- **KU Leuven:** Key areas are an overview of the current potentialities and know-how at KU Leuven, all of them being highly multidisciplinary: **medical technologies; bio-sciences & environment; matter, materials & energy; nature unlimited; manufacturing & ICT; arts, religion & culture; economy, law and society; human behaviour.**

- **UJ** has seven priority research areas: **Heritage** (identity of individuals and entire societies, language, civilizational challenges of modern world), **FutureSoc** (interdisciplinary research on social changes caused by the development of new technologies and the cognitive sciences), **BioS** (Structural and translational biology); **qLIFE** (better research for better quality of life, translational research: civilization diseases, reproductive health, regenerative medicine; drug development: mechanisms, targets, clinical trials); **SciMat** (design of advanced materials from models and theoretical tools via synthesis and characterization to applications); **DigiWorld** (digital world and cyber space); **Anthropocene** (the causes, paths and consequences of global environmental changes).
- **UP1**: UP1 is currently preparing a roadmap of research. Thematic alignment with Horizon Europe priorities and Cluster's Intervention Domains is a key priority. Una Europa's current and future focus areas (**one health, sustainable development, artificial intelligence, European Studies, Cultural Heritage**) are largely promoted, at the institutional level, including through our annual call for proposals. More specific research themes are defined at faculty and research unit levels, in concordance with the University and partner research organizations (such as CNRS) main priorities. Examples of research topics investigated and supported by either faculties or research units include: **war studies; democracy & social cohesion; liberties; Europe as a whole; environment & environmental vulnerability, sustainable transports; heritage studies; new forms of work; HSS at the interface with cognitive sciences; AI; transversal approaches to health; design and creative industry.**

In addition to strategic research areas, we also asked universities to identify their five to ten top research areas and explain how they were selected. Selection criteria mentioned included international and national evaluations (partially internationally peer-reviewed) and different types of external funding including ERC. For the analysis, we grouped the research fields in larger thematic areas, partially guided by already existing Una Europa focus areas, such as AI, One Health, sustainability, culture and creativity, European studies, science, industry, society, economy and social sciences, languages, regional studies, environment, etc. Several entries per thematic areas were possible.

Due to the spread of data, this exercise was of limited meaningfulness for identifying potential new Una Europa focus areas. However, the exercise does reveal that Una Europa focus areas largely reflect the strengths of the member institutions. Six out of eight universities regard research related to One Health (health 5/8, medicine 5/8) as well as sustainability as a strength. Seven out of eight named fields or disciplines related to cultural heritage. AI was listed by three institutions. Only one institution saw European Studies as a research strength. However, this Una Europa area has an education focus and as such is not a clearly defined field of research. Contributing disciplines such as the social sciences are rated excellent by six out of eight universities. We could identify potential clusters of strength in the fields of universe, matter and energy; biosciences & environment; health and medicine; ancient history; public policy, societies and democracy; climate; languages, and arts.

2.2.3. Multidisciplinary Practices and Structures

In the benchmarking questionnaire, we asked universities to identify multidisciplinary structures with varying degrees of institutionalization, such as centres, institutes, research initiatives, and graduate schools dedicated to a specific theme or geographical region. The premise of this question was based on the observation that many universities do not formulate top-down strategic research areas. In most cases, it was also unclear how defined strategic aims are implemented. Analysing existing structures thus served here as a proxy to identify resource priorities of universities as well as research strengths. Furthermore, we assume that collaborations between these structures could be an added value of Una Europa.

The analysis showed that universities maintain various types of multidisciplinary structures and support them in different ways. Support can entail the allocation of specific support services, funding, or increasing visibility. The founding of multidisciplinary centres or initiatives often originates in national and regional competitive funding.

These were either bottom-up calls or top-down funding schemes aiming at profiling, interdisciplinary research or the building of ecosystems with non-academic partners.

- **Interdepartmental centres** are interdisciplinary hubs and research communities between departments and faculties and interdepartmental industrial research centres. The departments or units are members of the centres. The centres provide services and share strategic goals. In some cases, these are built upon strategic initiatives. Researchers may have dual positions in both a department and the centre. This often leads to parallel structures which are problematic to manage.
- Units or department can also share **interdepartmental initiatives** that aim to build or strengthen strategic areas of multidisciplinary research. Support for these initiatives is provided as part of other organizational structures.
- **Independent research institutes located on university campuses** support research groups and individual researchers in networking. These research institutes mainly have independent management and research agendas.
- **Central research institutes** combine different disciplines and expertise under one organization and often aim to interdisciplinary research and may have a specific strategic research theme.
- The management practices and ways of organising vary, but this type of central research institutes often provides organizational structures for networking, research support services and provide grants.
- All universities offer **graduate schools** with inter- or multidisciplinary orientation.

We organized the multidisciplinary structures, many of them serving both SSH and STEM fields, according to Una Europa focus areas and also identified clusters of themes that are not yet represented by a focus area, such as urban studies and cognitive sciences. The clustering was not straightforward. For focus areas with a clearly defined focus, such as AI and data science, the matching was obvious, for focus areas that are still developing, such as One Health, less so. Many structures fitted with several focus areas, such as digital health. In addition, sustainability, which is also an individual Una Europa focus area, is reflected in the work of many structures.

We also listed institutes and centres aiming at stimulation of transdisciplinary research especially between SSH-STEM fields. Una Europa could use the learnings from these in future. We do not provide a full list of the many multidisciplinary structures in the social sciences and humanities, represented at all universities. Neither do we list structures in engineering and industry research, which are present at only some universities. The listing below is thus not comprehensive and should be considered only as an initial starting point for providing direction. The original listings will be available for future use on the Una Europa common data repository.

Sharing knowledge about multidisciplinary structures and initiatives could facilitate collaboration across focus areas and inspire bottom-up creation of new research questions. As Una Europa research collaboration is dynamically developing, this should ideally be a continuous process.

Focus Area Sustainability (Incl. Sustainable Development and Global Change)

Sustainability is a broad concept that brings together a variety of disciplinary perspectives, ranging from the bio sciences to the social sciences, from engineering to environmental humanities. The benchmarking questionnaire provided no specific definition of the term and did not specifically link to Una Europa activities or definitions. Given the openness of the term, many structures could be linked to this focus areas. Below are those listed with a primary focus on sustainability.

- **KU Leuven:** KU Leuven Institute for Mobility
- **UCM:** The Complutense Institute of Sociology - Contemporary Social Transformations; Institute of Geosciences (IGEO); Environmental Science (IUCA)

- **UH:** Helsinki Institute of Sustainability Science (Helsus); Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research (INAR); Thriving Nature--Towards Future Healthy Ecosystems; Helsinki Institute of Urban and Regional Studies (Urbaria)
- **UNIBO:** Alma Mater Institute on Healthy Planet (Alma Healthy Planet); Alma Mater Research Institute on Global Challenges and Climate Change (Alma Climate); Interdepartmental Research Centre for Environmental Sciences (CIRSA); Interdepartmental Centre for Industrial Research in Renewable Resources, Environment, Sea and Energy (CIRI); Renewable Resources, Environment, Sea and Energy (FRAME)
- **UP1:** LabEc DynamiTe (spatial and territorial dynamics); ArChal (global challenges in the light of the past); Sorbonne Sustainable Development association

Focus Area One Health

All universities have multidisciplinary structures in the fields of biomedicine, agriculture, food pharmaceuticals, or global change that can support research in the focus area One Health. With Helsinki One Health (HoH), only UH has an institutional network with a focus specifically on One Health.

Focus Area AI and Data Sciences

Six out of the eight universities maintain multidisciplinary structures in the fields of AI and data science. As AI and Data Sciences provide tools for solving problems in many research areas, these structures link to a variety of disciplines. Areas of application include among other digital humanities, biostatistics and bioinformatics, as well as engineering and industry related initiatives. Structures fitting into the focus area AI and Data Sciences also link to cognitive sciences, a field we listed separately below.

- **KU Leuven:** KU Leuven Digital Society Institute; Leuven.AI Institute for Artificial Intelligence; KU Leuven Institute of Physics-based Modeling for In Silico Health (ISI Health)
- **UCM:** Institute for Knowledge Technology; Department of Methodology of Behavioural Sciences
- **UEDIN:** The Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI)
- **UH:** Helsinki Centre for Data Science (HiDATA); Finnish Center for Artificial Intelligence (FCAI)
- **UNIBO:** Ercole De Castro Advanced Research Center on Electronic System (ARCES); Interdepartmental Centre for Industrial ICT Research (CIRI ICT); Biostatistics: Statistical Sciences and Medical Departments; Precision Farming: Electrical, Electronic, and Information Engineering Department, the Agricultural and Food Sciences Department; Alma Mater Research Institute for Human-Centred Artificial Intelligence (Alma Human AI)
- **UP1:** History of Knowledge, Technology and Beliefs (HaStec)

Focus Area Cultural Heritage

Only four out of eight Una universities answered that they feature multidisciplinary structures linked to cultural heritage. Note: A more in more in-depth analysis on resources in the culture and creative industries has been conducted as preparation for the CCI-KIC bid, the results of which are not included here.

- **UNIBO:** Research Center for interaction with Cultural and Creative Industries (CRICC)
- **UCM:** The Complutense Institute of Musical Sciences (ICCMU)
- **KU Leuven:** Institute for Cultural Heritage; Institute for the Study of the Transmission of Texts, Ideas and Images in Antiquity, the Middle Ages and the Renaissance
- **UP1:** The Time Machine Organisation (TMO); École des arts de la Sorbonne

Focus Area Europe and the World

- **FUB:** The John-F.-Kennedy Institute for North American Studies; The Institute for East European Studies; The Institute for Latin America Studies, The Berlin Graduate School of Muslim Cultures and

Societies; The Graduate School for North American Studies; The Graduate School for East Asian Studies

- **UH:** Centre for European Studies; Aleksanteri Institute: Finnish Centre for Russian and Eastern European Studies
- **UCM:** The Complutense Institute for International Studies (ICEI)**Cognitive Studies**

The substantial number of multidisciplinary structures focused on cognitive sciences and studies could be leveraged in a new Una Europa focus area.

- **FUB:** Center for Cognitive Neuroscience Berlin
- **UH:** Mind and Matter – Foundations of Information, Intelligence and Consciousness; UHealth – Interdisciplinary Research for Health and Well-being strengthens the UH research ecosystem to generate viable solutions for future health challenges.
- **UCM:** The University Institute of Religious Sciences; The Multidisciplinary Institute (IP): three units “Brain Mapping Unit”, “Fluid Unit” and “Lasers and Molecular Beams Unit”; Institute for Knowledge Technology
- **KU Leuven:** Institute for Micro- and Nano-scale Integration; Brain Institute
- **JU:** Copernicus Center
- **UP1:** The Matrice Memory Equipment of Excellence

Urban Development

Several universities had multidisciplinary structures with aims supporting urban development area. Many of them also interlink with sustainability.

- **UH:** Helsinki Institute of Urban and Regional Studies (Urbaria)
- **UCM:** The Complutense Institute of Management Science (ICCA);
- **KU Leuven:** Urban Studies Institute; KU Leuven Institute for Mobility
- **UNIBO:** Advanced School of Studies on the City and Territory (SSCT)
- **UP1:** Dynamite (spatial and territorial dynamics projects)

Structures with Focus on Enhancing Transdisciplinary SSH-STEM Research

These structures could play a pivotal role in the development of inter-, trans-, and multidisciplinary research in Una Europa.

- **KU Leuven:** Leuven Institute for the Future (research incubator supporting transdisciplinary research)
- **UEDIN:** The Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI) (the navigation of complex futures; arts, humanities, the social sciences, data science, engineering, the natural sciences, medicine)
- **UH:** Helsinki Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities (HSSH)
- **UJ:** Copernicus Center (advanced interdisciplinary studies at intersections of natural sciences, humanities and social sciences)
- **UP1:** Sorbonne Art Gallery (art-science research programme)

2.2.4. Strategic Partnerships and Existing Collaborations within Una Europa

The questionnaire also surveyed existing collaborations (pilots, initiatives or strategic partnerships on R&I or research support development) on multi- and bilateral level as well as existing collaboration between Una Europa universities. The benchmarking did not entail a systematic analysis of, for example, joint Horizon projects. There are, however, many Horizon Europe and Erasmus+ funded projects with several Una Europa partners that could straight support Una Europa collaboration development like Ritrain+ in the field of human

capital and research infrastructures. Evaluate project aims to developing the assessment of strategic partnerships, which systematises quality management practices.

The responses provided in the questionnaire exemplify first the various forms of collaborations which differ in geographical scope (local, regional, national, European and global), in terms of partner (individual institutions, associations, initiatives, cities) and in terms of purpose and theme: Innovation, thematic, values, academic purposes).

Collaborations among Una Europa partners exist both directly (joint Horizon research projects, joint seed funding, strategic partnerships) as well as on multilateral level within larger consortia such as Unica, The Guild, LERU etc. According to information provided on websites and the questionnaire, following bilateral strategic partnerships exist between Una Europa partners: KU Leuven with UH, UEDIN, JU and LEI; UCM with UH and FUB; UEDIN with UH, KU Leuven and LEI; UH with UEDIN and KU Leuven, JU with UEDIN, UNIBO and KU Leuven; KU Leuven with UH, UEDIN, JU and LEI. 2

Association	FUB	KU L	LEI ²	UCM	UEDIN	UH	UJ	UNIBO	UP1
<u>EASSH</u>									via EUROPAUM
<u>EUA</u>							indirect		
<u>EUROPAEUM</u>									
<u>EVALUATE</u>									
<u>LERU</u>									
<u>OpenU</u>									
<u>The Coimbra Group</u>									
<u>The Guild</u>									
<u>TMO</u>									
<u>UNICA</u>									

Table 1. Memberships in other Higher Education Alliances

2.3. Key Outcomes for the Una Europa R&I Strategy

The analysis provided evidence that the strategies and policies of the Una Europa universities reflect the values of Una Europa as a European University Initiative of large research universities, values that are formulated in the Una Europa manifesto. The analysis also showed that values are consistent across Una Europa universities and no outliers exist. These values should be reflected also in the Una Europa R&I strategy.

The benchmarking did not provide a conclusive picture which research areas or fields would lend themselves as new focus areas for Una Europa but confirms that existing Una Europa focus areas, developed as part of the 1Europe project, mostly reflect both strategic choices and areas of research strengths. Additional areas of excellence that are shared among a critical number of Una Europa partners are: universe, matter and energy; biosciences & environment; health and medicine; ancient history; public policy, societies and democracy; climate; languages, and arts.

² University of Leiden joined Una Europa in 2022 and was hence not included in the benchmarking. Information provided in this table is based on the institutional websites.

In certain field such as cognitive science and urban studies, most Una Europa partners possess multidisciplinary structures that could be leveraged towards new Una Europa research collaborations. Several universities maintain institutes that are already focused on interdisciplinary research. Their expertise should be utilized in future Una Europa work.

The multitude of partnerships Una Europa members maintain on various levels is both a challenge and an opportunity for Una Europa as a consortium. On the one hand, Una Europa is just one of many partnerships our universities are part of. On the other hand, Una Europa provides opportunities to link to these existing ecosystems and potentially allow members to profit from existing collaborations. A first example is the 2021 call EIT KIC Cultural and Creative Sector Industries, for which Una Europa joined the bid of the consortium Innovation by Creative Economy (ICE) coordinated by the Fraunhofer Institute. Going beyond this, the challenge for Una Europa will be to develop signature added value for the universities to ensure sufficient resources and attention of the leadership. Strategic thematic partnerships that provide robust structures of collaboration and can possibly be leveraged within Una Europa will be explored further in Una.Resin.

3. Una Europa R&I Strategy Workshop (Sep 2021)

3.1. Methodology

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the originally planned physical workshop could not be organised. Instead, we developed a concept for an online workshop. The aim of the workshop was 1) to identify **research themes** the Una Europa community deems as important in the future to solve the **grand challenges** and 2) to identify **enablers and barriers to international research collaboration**.

Una.Resin WP1 invited six researchers per institution to a three-hour online workshop on September 22, 2021. Most participants were senior academics who also fulfilled roles as dean or head of departments. The workshop was facilitated by the think tank Demos Helsinki.

In preparation of the workshop, participants were asked to conclude a pre-assignment using the online platform Flinga. The workshop commenced with three keynote speeches which introduced the concept of grand challenges. For the discussion, participants were divided into multi-disciplinary and multi-institutional groups.

3.2. Workshop Program

Pre-Assignment using Flinga On-line Canvas

- **Enablers and good practices of international collaboration**
Thinking of your own experiences, please describe shortly enablers and good practices that could serve as an inspiration when considering international research collaboration in terms of infrastructures, multidisciplinary research, ecosystems, research lifecycle (ex: sharing, management, support, training personnel, opening collaboration to non-academic organizational partners and citizens).
- **Wild cards of research themes**
Considering the current common excellence and focus areas of the Una Europa universities, the existing Una Europa focus areas, Horizon Europe key strategic orientations and clusters, and the grand challenges presented on the Flinga Whiteboard as inspiration, which multidisciplinary research themes can you see emerging? What should be considered relevant towards 2030 and beyond? Please add your ideas of research themes and link them to the relevant Una Europa strengths and grand challenges. You may also suggest additional research themes or grand challenges that you consider important towards 2030 and beyond.

Keynotes

- Welcoming Words, Prof. James Smith, Una.Resin Project Coordinator, Chair of the Una Europa Research Strategy Group, Vice Principal International University of Edinburgh
- An Introduction to Grand Challenges, Aleksi Neuvonen, Demos Helsinki
- The EU's Approach to International R&I Collaboration in a Changing World, Nienke Buisman, Head of Unit, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Global Approach & International Partnerships, International Cooperation

Group Discussion

An identical set of on-line working canvases were provided to each discussion group. The canvases included directions and guiding time frames for each canvas. A facilitator, appointed to each group, was supporting the groups how to use the canvases, when needed.

- **Part 1: Which multidisciplinary research themes can you see emerging? What should be considered relevant towards 2030 and beyond?**

Participants were asked to suggest research themes which they consider to be of high relevance in the next decade and beyond. The two sub questions were:

1. A theme that you're familiar with and that is impactful and important for the future.
2. A theme that is important and impactful for the future, but not so familiar to you and you want to learn more about. After this the groups discussed the ideas of each group member.

The key note speeches, pre-distributed materials (list of societal challenges, Horizon Europe priorities, Una Europa focus areas and Una Europa strengths) and a pre-assignment served as inspiration.

- **Part 2: Enablers and barriers of the international research collaboration**

Participants were asked to conceive a shared imaginary research project using the outcomes of part 1 and then discuss enablers and barriers clustered around four themes: research infrastructures, ecosystems, multidisciplinary opportunities and research lifecycle. They were asked to consider following parameters: sharing, management, support, training personnel, diversity and inclusion, opening collaboration to non-academic partners and citizens (Fig 4).

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Fig. 1. Working deck of the group discussions

3.3. Synthesis of the Discussions

Part 1: Which multidisciplinary research themes can you see emerging? What should be considered relevant towards 2030 and beyond?

Many themes connected to the current Una Europa focus areas and crosscut with each other as well as with the grand challenges. Key themes that correspond directly to existing Una Europa focus areas included data science and AI, health and wellbeing, cultural heritage & identity, and sustainable and inclusive transitions, globally and in societies. Other themes were democracy and governance, European public policies (NEB, Green Deal, SDGs), inclusive societies/ societal inclusion and social cohesion as well as the indirect impact and economic and social spill over, future of food, urban studies, migration and mobility as well as neurosciences. Future materials emerged as a topic already prior to the workshop and was subsequently incorporated as an additional focus area in the 2022 1Europe proposal.

Part 2: Enablers and barriers of the international research collaboration

Research Infrastructures

Participants regarded research infrastructures and resources as pivotal enablers for collaborative research and community building. Knowing what kind of infrastructures (including data sets) are available at partner institutions was deemed important, for example via catalogues of equipment. Networks of research laboratories can be formed by enhancing the mobility of researchers, staff, and students (possible formats: research retreats, job shadowing, Erasmus+ staff exchange). Infrastructures should also incorporate the broader civil society, among others with the aim of knowledge dissemination.

Data Infrastructures

Sharing of data and data infrastructures was a topic that was discussed in terms of both “enablers” and “obstacles” from many points of view: Infrastructures, ecosystems and multidisciplinary research. Researchers highlighted an urgent need for enhancing processes of storing, sharing and accessing data. Existing platforms are not working efficiently. Particularly health and clinical data is hard if not impossible to share at this point. European data regulations (data protection etc.) lead to a competitive disadvantage if compared to e.g., U.S. and Chinese researchers. Furthermore, there is a lack of harmonization between national, EU and international regulations.

Una Europa provides an opportunity to multiply the scale of data access, but in order to achieve this, barriers in the form of regulations, finances and incompatible systems need to be removed. Una Europa could, for example, develop trans-national standardized ways and facilitate (virtual) RIRs to collect, store and share data. The added value of the systems for science must remain at the centre of the endeavour. Exchange across disciplines and research ecosystems should be enabled. The overhead needs to be kept as simple as possible and the disruption of data owners at a minimum. In case of data being restricted to a certain location, people can also move under the condition that agreements are in place to share data. Una Europa researchers could, for example, be affiliated with other teams or institutes at partner universities.

Ecosystems

The discussions evolved around two kinds of ecosystems, those consisting only of researchers and research institutions and those including non-academic partners, since we did not define ecosystems in the task. This created some confusion and highlighted the need to define the term if used in the Una Europa R&I strategy.

Participants pointed out that ecosystems work under the premise of a common language and open-mindedness. Sharing of data is another crucial enabler. In research ecosystems, the circulation of researchers enables the cross-fertilization of research groups. Also, technical and administrative staff (and with them their knowledge) should be shared. Institutions need management staff who can map available resources on an ongoing basis

and exchange listings with their counterparts at partner institutions. Una Europa could build joint information tools on R&I ecosystems in key areas (in common format for all institutions, including description of ecosystems open to all Una Europa members). Also, support in identifying funding opportunities and grant writing was seen as important.

Functioning ecosystems are using existing capacities and make them sustainable. Building an ecosystem should be facilitated by identification of promising themes/topics and appropriate levels for networking. Una Europa should also invest in networks with non-academic partners, not only companies, and create novel ways to engage with citizens for example by organizing research retreats which include policy makers or offer training sessions to citizens on specific concepts. During projects, bridges should be built between different projects to widen the community and connect to the business environment and policy makers.

Multidisciplinary Opportunities in Research

Researchers recognized the high value of multidisciplinary research despite the multiple barriers that need time and effort to overcome (differences in languages, institutions, evaluation traditions, priorities, difficulty to publish interdisciplinary work, risky career pursuit esp. for young scholars, etc.). Institutions have to acknowledge that these projects cannot always be fitted into departmental structures and need to create incentives. Multidisciplinarity provides new approaches in science such as open science and citizen science and enables the embedding of external stakeholders, research beyond academia, and citizens.

Participants suggested a variety of measures how multidisciplinary research can be incentivized, among others by thematic networks that are headquartered at one partner institution, the creation of meeting spaces, mapping of expertise of Una Europa researchers and the existing ecosystems, enhanced mobility among researchers and students also across disciplines, decoupling of certain funding from publication outputs, the introduction of interdisciplinary approaches at the universities and national evaluation processes.

Research Lifecycle: What is Needed for an Ideal Project / Long-term Collaboration?

Researchers noted that sufficient incentives are required from the outset. While seed funding is a typical incentive, long-term funding and the procurement of resources, time, and effective project management tools are more important. An ideal collaboration would allow full/easier access to the facilities and infrastructures of the other universities. Furthermore, Una Europa should promote collaborations that go beyond the life of single projects or grants.

General Remarks on Una Europa Collaboration

A consensus emerged that Una Europa should provide support in particular to early career scholars. Sustainability and inclusivity were seen as common values in most discussions. These need to be taken seriously and be embedded in all activities and strategies of Una Europa. The organisational and hierarchical distinction between academic and professional staff for example should be overcome with the aim to work together as team. Researchers desire long-term support for their projects as well as for funding and pre-award assistance.

The feedback from attendees was positive and facilitated co-creation, however some participants found that they lacked skills and traditions for this kind of multi-/interdisciplinary workshop approach and wished for a better introduction to this kind of working method. Additionally, Una Europa is not yet very well-known at the member universities, thus the motivation to look for future orientation for this collaboration was not always clear.

We found that research themes raised in this workshop were often crosscutting several grand challenges reflecting that these challenges are interlinked, cannot be treated as separate phenomena and require complex solutions. Furthermore, we found that research interests and questions formulated by researchers do not neatly fit the frameworks as formulated by political decision-makers. Terminologies and approaches such as “grand challenges” are hence not always the most fruitful way to engage researchers in a workshop like this one. Researchers formulate their interests within the terminology and culture of their discipline.

4. One Health SSC Workshop (Feb 2022)

4.1. Methodology

The Una.Resin WP1 project managers from UH and FUB attended the first workshop organised by the Una Europa One Health Self Steering Committee in Bertinoro, Italy in February 2022. The goals of the workshop were to:

- 1) consolidate the Una OH SSC through a better knowledge of the Una Europa partner institutions
- 2) improve the level of awareness of the alliance and ongoing and upcoming projects
- 3) finalize the final OH Future workshop document as a position paper
- 4) design the first Una OH summer school
- 5) define a possible joint or multiple PhD pathway
- 6) identify and conceptualize possible joint research projects.

For WP1, the workshop provided an opportunity to present goals and preliminary outcomes of Una.Resin to the researchers and consult them on upcoming tasks of WP1, namely the implementation of **pilots** (task 1.11 according to GA) to facilitate research collaboration and the conceptualization of an **online platform** (task 1.12) for supporting R&I collaboration within Una Europa, formats that should be sustainable beyond the project lifecycle of Una.Resin. The workshop also allowed WP to discuss elements of a **Una Europa funding strategy** (task 1.9) that shall include possible funding opportunities as well as practices to support match-making and common proposals.

On the first day, WP1 project managers presented Una.Resin's goals and specifically the R&I strategy process. This was followed up by discussions on the 1Europe roll-out, Una Europa international strategy preparation, as well as on collaborations with the private sector. On the second day, participants worked in rotating groups on four topics, namely the summer school, possible joint PhDs, the position paper, and possible joint research projects.

WP1 project managers facilitated the discussion on the last topic together with Una Europa Senior external funding officer. The initial goal was to identify common interests in the Horizon Europe 2022 call. Due to the early stages of Una Europa One Health collaboration and the short deadlines, this turned out to be not feasible. Thus, it was decided to conduct a workshop series, both online and in person, for OH as **Una.Resin pilots** in fall 2022. Co-organized with Una Europa vzw's senior external funding advisor, the workshops should facilitate joint proposals for Horizon Europe 2023 calls.

In addition to the discussion of Horizon Europe calls, WP1 had prepared discussion points on ecosystems, young researchers as Una Europa's main target group, the effectiveness of co-creation workshops, as well as funding opportunities. The discussion of these topics was continued in the plenary as well as informally during breaks.

4.2. Key Outcomes for the R&I Strategy

Una Europa Support for Funding

The researchers participating in the workshop had so far limited experience with Horizon Europe funded projects and indicated a strong interest in applying for Horizon Europe funding together. As mentioned, this will be taken up by WP1 pilots.

Una Europa as a Facilitator of Interdisciplinary Research

Participating researchers saw the value of Una Europa both as possibility to find new collaborations as well as in the realm of research support. They articulated a need to shift research paradigms within OH and increase interdisciplinarity in order to solve major challenges. Identifying researchers outside of one's fields is generally considered difficult. Researchers supported the suggestion that Una Europa could play a major role in facilitating the identification of researchers in other fields with whom research questions could be tackled. This was in fact seen as a key added value. As an attendee put it: "Science is about finding new knowledge. Una Europa can help us to find researchers who work on the same questions, but from different angles."

To build a multidisciplinary community within focus areas, several suggestions were made which will be further explored within Una.Resin:

- An interdisciplinary **Una Europa Fair** with researchers from various disciplines and external stakeholders
- An **online platform** which increases the visibility and fields of expertise of Una Europa researchers, allows match-making and collaboration to create high quality consortia for acquiring competitive funding. The platform should allow the search for specific profiles and keywords and allow the posting of calls of interest, in particular in the interest of early career researchers.
- **Match-making** specifically aimed at young researchers, for example through summer-schools
- **Seed funding** to support multidisciplinary initiatives (already existing on Una Europa level)
- **Una Europa training for PhD students** could include training for methods and tools to enhance multidisciplinary collaboration (for example research methods of different fields and ways to write multidisciplinary research publication).

To be able to communicate the aims of Una Europa OH to researchers from other fields and potential non-academic collaborators, the SSC agreed that a vision for a truly multidisciplinary field needs to be created. — work the SSC has already started within the OH focus area. Una OH has run an own foresight workshop series that included scenario planning towards 2050. To expand the narrow concept of Una Europa OH, it was suggested to expand Una Europa OH to Una Planetary Health. The concept of **Scenario workshop formats** could also be scaled other Una Europa focus areas to build community.

Una Europa Internationalization

In addition to collaboration on European level, OH researchers considered global collaboration—particularly with African actors—extremely important. The OH network already possesses substantial expertise in building meaningful collaborations that add value for all parties rather than burden partners with unsustainable or ineffective assistance. This knowledge thus should be taken into account when developing the Una Europa's international collaborations.

Collaboration with Non-Academic Partners

Initially, the discussion about key non-academic partners focused on the private sector, mainly pharmaceutical companies. However, in the course of the discussion also institutions such as the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) were named as important collaborators. In addition, possibilities to attract venture capital for OH-start-ups were discussed. Participants agreed that concept of One Health needs to be well communicated to increase awareness of the concept among collaborators and venture capitalists.

A strategic question that remains open concerns the question of how to support Una Europa ecosystem building in a sustainable way. How much support and initiative should be provided by Una Europa (i.e., Una Europa vzw with Una resources provided by the universities) and how much by university services? Should the initiative of for example reaching out to the ECDE be taken by Una Europa vzw or the SSC?

Data Management: Challenge to Collaboration

Similar to the Una.Resin R&I Strategy Workshop, OH researchers lamented the difficulties of data management and data sharing in general and across institutions.

Una Europa for Early Career Researchers

Participants agreed that Una Europa should focus on early-career researchers, though it was emphasized that senior researchers are also needed to build sustainable and fruitful networks. Una Europa could enable early career researchers to diversify their networks by a) the mere virtue of the Una Europa community, which would allow low-threshold informal connections with colleagues from partner universities and b) by an ever-closer collaboration among the research services. Sharing infrastructures and ecosystems would also benefit early career researchers.

Several ideas were developed as to what a Una Europa training for PhD students could look like. It was suggested to provide training specialised in methods and funding opportunities to enhance multidisciplinary collaboration. Trainings would also support networking. The mobility of PhD students should also be funded. There are existing funding instruments which could be explored, for example Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, as well as national funding schemes for short and long-term research stays abroad. Una Europa could also fund 4-years scholarships with an opportunity to visit other Una Europa university. Co-finance open access publications and even start an PhD thesis series or Una Europa OH journal (targeted to young researchers but also others). It was also suggested to build Una Europa dissertation committees. Industry funded PhD-programs and training positions were mentioned as further options to benefit from common ecosystem.

5. Una Europa 2030 Strategy

The Una Europa R&I strategy is developed in conjunction with the Una Europa 2030 strategy. The community consultations of the Una Europa 2030 strategy have been designed together with Una.Resin WP1. Insights of the Una.Resin process have also fed into the drafting of the 2030 strategy.

5.1. Online Consultation of the Una Europa Community

5.1.1. Methodology

As part of [Una Europa 2030 strategy](#) preparation, an interactive process was launched using [Viima](#), an online innovation platform that facilitates the collection of ideas and topics, their interlinkage as well visualization. WP1 was involved in the formulation of the questions for the consultation, which was open from 6th May 2021 until 16th July 2022. Anyone with an email address of the eight Una Europa universities was invited to provide ideas and inputs.

The lead questions for the community were the following: Where do we go from here? What do we stand for in the future? How do we want to study? What kind of research will be relevant? What will this alliance look like? Where can we, as Una Europa, be stronger together?

Participants were encouraged to enter ideas, a key issue, development, or factor that will impact on the future of universities and Una Europa and explain why they considered the idea as important. Ideas could be attributed to categories or marked with a hashtag selected from the following list:

Act global: #Europe #EU #Africa, #internationalcollaboration #greentransition #sustainability #climate #digital #impact #innovation #globaltalent #capacitybuilding #responsibility

Connect with our communities: #community #communitybuilding, #connectingecosystems, #quadruplehelix, #commons, #servicetosociety, #mobility, #virtualmobility, #hybridmobility, #staffexchange #studentexchange #partnerships #citizenscience #labourmarket

Enhance our values: #diversity #inclusion #genderequality #wideningparticipation #multilingualism #multiculturalism #independence #intellectualplayground #empowerment #openness #intersectionality #anti-racism #accessibility #truth #learning #freedom #rigour

Learn for life: #studentcentred #flexiblelearning #innovation #quality #graduatesforthefuture #learninginthefuture #accessibility #researchbasedlearning #studentcocreation #globalcompetences

Conduct research for the future: #infrastructure #innovation #impact #participatoryresearch #capacitybuilding #researchmobility #researchcareers #youngresearchers #collaborativeresearch #excellence #teamsience #openscience #methodologies #data #imagination

Use your wildcard

5.1.2. Results

Participants of the Viima survey engaged in a genuine discussion about visions for Una Europa. Altogether 131 ideas, 126 comments, and 1078 “like” -reactions were added to the Viima board with responses being equally distributed among Una Europa universities. The amount of interaction with the platform indicated that Viima is an effective tool for this type of community consultation. Most responses, however, came from administrative and service professionals, but there were also answers from several academics from young researchers to the dean’s level. The emphasis of the administrative professionals in the answer was likely due to the fact that Una Europa still lacks visibility among academics and that Una Europa collaborations are at an early stage. For the analysis, all

inputs were transferred to Atlas.ti, which allowed an in-depth inter-relational investigation of the results. In the following, we present a synthesis of the opinions and ideas formulated on Viima.

Guiding Principles of Una Universities

Academic freedom following the Humboldtian tradition, the university as sanctuary of thought, academics/students and critical thinking was emphasized in the Viima answers. Respondents argued that Una Europa should follow global trends in higher education and research policy while keeping to the core functions and values of the universities. Diversity and inclusiveness were raised in many answers.

Sustainability

Sustainability and green values emerged in many answers, alongside the demand to embed sustainability in all actions of Una Europa universities. Activities should be aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals and other global priorities. Una Europa, respondents stated, can provide global answers to global problems while Una students and researchers can emerge as new leaders of global change. Environmental humanities could be incorporated in all Una Europa programs as they encourage to think about transitional societies and ways to deal with an ever-changing world.

Enhancing Collaboration of Management and Research Professionals

Respondents suggested a variety of ideas how to put collaboration into practice, including a digital campus “Una Hub”, joint education and training; joint data repositories to share information and knowledge; mobility programs such as staff exchanges and an interuniversity library. In addition, it was suggested that Una Europa universities could share good management practices, exchange institutional research and exploit knowledge bases together.

At large, respondents regarded digitalisation of practices, systems, and data management as central for community building and collaboration in Una Europa.

Una Europa as Research Community

Strengthening the Una Europa community by collaboration and communication was also a major focus of the answers. To enhance Una Europa collaboration, some participants saw a need for joint Una governing practices of management and services, a joint vision as well as joint guiding principles, including those concerning the engagement with non-academic institutions. Mobility among and collaboration between teaching and research staff was seen as key for building common services. Other respondents, however, argued that networks and infrastructures should be kept decentralized, following the principle of “Unity in diversity!”

Interdisciplinarity

Interdisciplinarity will become a key mode of knowledge production according to many participants, who stressed the need for integrating perspectives and methods of different disciplines in solving complex problems and future challenges. In order to support interdisciplinary work and increase the excellence of each university, Una Europa could pool resources from all institutions and facilitate larger and highly ambitious research groups. Una Europa could match partners for top-down calls on societal challenges. Echoing a point brought up in the Una.Resin R&I workshop, respondents highlighted that universities need to consider how to credit researchers engaging in multidisciplinary research in career assessments.

Una Europa for Early Career Researchers

An overwhelming number of participants thought that Una Europa should be particularly geared towards early career researchers. One suggested measure included seed funding for PhDs prior to their post-doc phase. Una should also organize Una Europa visiting programs and networking opportunities for PhD students and postdocs such as joint summer schools and research methods training. Joint doctoral programs could focus on complex challenges and could be funded by MSCA.

Diversity

Respondents stressed that the Una Europa community should support diversity and intersectional justice. One respondent raised the issues of talented university drop-outs and the need to support them. The quote below provides a reminder that the Una Europa R&I strategy should not replicate and reinforce existing career structures that harm diversity. (Note: An Una Europa Human Capital Strategy is developed by Una.Resin's WP3).

"The ones I knew happened to come from underrepresented populations at university level (working class, ethnic minorities), and/or presented psychological traits which made today's academia an unfit environment for them (leading to ex: burnouts). The university of the future would take this loss of talent seriously by studying what makes it happen and see how to propose ways for this talent to thrive. The current highly competitive international environment selects impressive people to staff universities, but it also squeezes out no-less (sometimes even more) impressive students who may have benefitted from a redesign of the conditions for success in academia. Besides specific challenges applicable to students coming from "minority" backgrounds, exceptional resistance to stress and pressure has become a sine qua non criterion for success in Academia, whereas one could have expected intelligence, relevance, hard work and originality to be sufficient." ..."The present structure does not select for the brightest minds, but for the most resilient personalities, including physical ability (ex: to tolerate sleep deprivation during PhD period). That's why the diversity shrinks the higher you climb on the academic career ladder."

Una Europa Internationalization

Building global networks and partners beyond Europe emerged as a recurrent theme. Respondents considered global collaboration of Una Europa crucial. Due to the importance of the continent for the EU and the availability of funding, collaborations with universities in Africa were mentioned as particularly important. Una Europa could build a network of Una Europa spokespeople across the globe and serve as a hub to connect universities from different continents.

It was also suggested that Una Europa could develop support for academics at risk by sharing information about employment opportunities, fund dedicated chairs and doctoral scholarships, and offer trainings to integrate scholars into the European research system.

Suggestions of Joint Research Projects and Collaborations

The list below illustrates the diversity of ideas put forward by the participants of the survey. The responses are edited for clarity.

- **Research on universities in a changing world:** *This kind of knowledge could serve in the decision making regarding the other activities of universities.*
- **Una Europa scientific supercomputing centre:** *Supercomputing research and Bigdata centre for Una Europa.*
- **Experimenting with blockchain technologies:** *Building a blockchain infrastructure within Una Europa partners would allow us not to miss the next generation innovation which will have numerous and unthinkable applications, from cryptocurrencies to digital certificates, data management and privacy.*
- **Una Europa with Africa:** *Applied mathematics is a great pilot topic for such collaboration, as language barriers are at the minimum with math, and there are many potential uses of modelling and computational math in developing societies.*
- **Fields as foundation for life:** *Nature and the rural world sustain the cities because we obtain fruits, vegetables, and meat from the countryside. But it not only contributes that, extensive cattle avoid fires since they clean the forests and allow biodiversity in the environment. However, depopulation will end all that and that will be chaos, so we must support farmers. We also have to investigate improvements in agriculture and avoid depopulation.*
- **Preserve the heritage of the media:** *The media are the lifeblood of democracy. Preserving, studying and analysing them and making them available to society as informational and documentary heritage is a pending challenge in Europe.*

5.2. Eight Questions for Eight Institutions

5.2.1. Methodology

In addition to the Viima community consultation, the Una Europa 2030 strategy process also included a consultation of the Una Europa institutions, which were asked to answer eight questions about the future of Una Europa community. The target group of the questionnaire was the Una Europa main institutional contacts, who collected each institution's answers.

1. **Go together:** Which role will the Una Europa partners play in your university's strategy in 2030? To what extent do you see integration of activities and governance developing between Una Europa partners by then?
2. **Develop the network's framework:** What kind of legal and governance framework will be needed to govern the network in 2030? Will the Una Europa vzw construction still be fit for purpose? And where will the money come from?
3. **Learn for life:** To what extent will you share your teaching and training with Una partners and what role will Una Europa joint degrees play in 2030? How can Una Europa partners continue to innovate together?
4. **Attract the best:** How will the Una Europa institutions recruit students, academics, and staff in 2030 – individually or together? How can joining forces lead to increasing the attractiveness of the institutions?
5. **Conduct research for the future:** How strongly will the individual research strategies and infrastructures be linked in 2030 and what will the aligned strategy look like?
6. **Connect with our communities:** How will we facilitate the connection of the eight regional ecosystems with its many stakeholders from business, academia, culture and politics into a European network? And to what degree can the network enhance your own institution's agenda for civic engagement locally?
7. **Enhance our values:** Which values should the network actively promote, for which should it be known in 2030 – academic freedom, sustainability, diversity, research and teaching excellence, gender equality etc.?
8. **Act global:** How can Una Europa become a role model for tackling global challenges? How can we as a network have an impact globally?

5.2.2. Key Outcomes for the Una Europa R&I Strategy

Strategic Role of the Una Europa Network

Una Europa is a highly prioritized strategic network for the Una Europa universities. Most universities stated that aims and practices of this alliance were likely to impact their own strategic choices and policies. The desired comprehensiveness of long-term flexible collaboration was seen as important added value: "This relationship is of a different nature to other agreements, as it seeks to be deeper and to establish more complex links." According to the survey, being part of Una Europa enhances the attractiveness and high-quality standards of each partner and provides a possibility to increase the impact of the member universities as societal actors, for example by teaching critical thinking as a basis a functioning democracy and enhancing the commitment to the SDGs.

Una Europa Focus Areas

Una Europa could become a role model for tackling global challenges by promoting joint initiatives for relevant cultural and societal issues, in particular the SDGs. Most respondents agreed that Una Europa should continue working in the current focus areas, but also identify other focus areas and support bottom-up initiatives. Collaboration in certain focus areas was seen as a way to increase excellence.

The suggestions made to justify the choice of research areas and the arguments for their key aims varied significantly in the answers. Considering the variety of views, methods to choose future research priorities need to be further discussed in the Una Europa R&I strategy process.

- Una Europa should define shared, challenge-based research themes to focus efforts, spur collaboration and bring together researchers from different disciplines. Research topics should be broad enough so that they are relevant for researchers from a wide spectrum of disciplines, while at the same time being concrete enough to enable meaningful ecosystem building.
- There should be a flexible and efficient mechanism to identify future priorities of research. This process should not be a purely top-down action but include consultation and dialogue with the Una Europa research community, including PhD students, early career researchers as well as the stakeholders.
- Even if Una Europa was to define commonly accepted focus areas for research, there should also be space for bottom-up initiatives or even only bottom-up approaches, without any top-down preferences for priority research fields. Una Europa should have categories with both top-down signature projects and also bottom-up peer-to-peer collaborations. Practices and criteria need to be developed for prioritizing topics, such as for example the number of partners involved.
- Future focus areas should be chosen by a carefully planned top-down approach aiming to excellence. We should identify several strategic fields or research areas where our research could be particularly strong or there is untapped potential for partners' respective strengths to supplement each other. Una Europa could even establish virtual excellence centres around these.
- Una Europa should develop practices to bring researchers together beyond their own networks (e.g. STEM-SH) to build interdisciplinary consortia for challenge-based top-down funding calls.
- It is important to look for emerging research fields. Una Europa should test bold research hypothesis instead of the publish-or-perish attitude that aims to get funding.

Building an Una Europa Ecosystem

This was found to be a very ambitious goal. However, Una Europa is in an excellent position to pool existing expertise and share best practices. The geographic coverage of Una Europa is a clear benefit.

Building the ecosystems requires funding for research as well as resources for facilitation, training, and community relations. Una Europa should develop a systematic partnership programme with clear objectives for teaching and learning as well as research collaboration. The joint ecosystem should be based on Una Europa's shared challenge-based research focus areas. Rather than an abstract entity, the eco-system should be considered as a network of meaningful connections.

Academia-business collaboration and start-up creation as well as exploring ways in which current focus areas (perhaps cultural heritage in particular) can create opportunities to connect with other actors like festivals, museums, etc- were considered important. Una Europa could initiate a widening of participation and use the great diversity of students and researchers as inspiration and guidance on the possible ways of engaging with different communities and their cultures.

Una Europa could define specific working groups to incorporate representatives of local stakeholders. Una Europa stakeholders should be invited to Una fairs, forums, and other events.

International Collaboration

International Una Europa networking was seen to be particularly meaningful in research aimed solving global challenges, it was therefore considered an important goal to network beyond Europa.

Collaborations should be built strategically on existing relationships and universities with similar research aims. Una Europa should provide shared and co-created opportunities for collaboration and share knowhow, good

practices, cooperation formats, and, where possible, resources and infrastructures with the partners. Una Europa should also look for opportunities to connect with local ecosystems. Scalable models for research collaboration between institutions, in connection to the international campuses, should be developed and implemented in various disciplines and with different partners.

Africa was mentioned several times in the answers as a possible geographical focus. Una Europa has great potential for impact creation and excellent opportunities to gain significant external funding in collaboration with African partners. EU investment in Africa is fragmented. This is a risk facing efforts by individual universities as well. Una Europa could have significant impact on sustainable development by setting up a thematically concentrated network. The Una Europa partners could also influence the agenda of the EU-AU strategy together and the African partners of the Una Europa universities will speak with a stronger voice through the alliance.

Una Europa could also create a close partnership with an alliance of universities from non-EU Eastern European countries as well as with world-leading universities from the US and Asia.

Practices to Support Una Europa Research Collaboration

Una Europa should create a strategic platform to support joint research and provide the necessary framework to easily implement joint initiatives in education and research. The goal should be to develop methods and tools for doing research together as an every-day habit and support deep remote research partnerships. Lean management of common activities should be based on sharing best and simplest possible administrative procedures, developed during the years of cooperation. Una Europa should keep on striving towards openness and low hierarchy in its governance and interactions.

Una Europa flexible support and seamless collaboration between the administrative and professional staff is key to developing the Una Europa framework to support collaboration in teaching and research. Una Europa vzw is essential for coordinating collaboration beyond individual projects and support external funding seeking communication and community building.

Una Europa should develop a comprehensive framework and a platform for systematic collaboration which extends beyond research to teaching and learning, to professional services, and even to external partnerships is a special character of this network to be nurtured. Strengthening collaboration at the unit level is essential to ensure balance between bottom-up and top-down initiatives. Still, Una Europa should be selective with the activities, to ensure that resources are well spent and that project scopes are not overextended. The network should also be aware of individual rules and regulations. It is essential to provide balanced and inclusive participation opportunities of various stakeholders in the decision-making processes.

Suggested measures to support Una Europa research collaboration:

- Una Europa partners should ensure access to important research infrastructures for all Una Europa researchers (according to transparent, participatory, and innovative standards).
- Data sharing infrastructures are essential for collaboration. Una Europa should also create a legal framework to ensure easy exchange of research data among Una Europa partners.
- Increasing awareness of research carried out at partner universities and matchmaking is needed.
 - A digital platform for matchmaking, coupled with mechanisms facilitating application for joint grant proposals, should be developed.
 - An Una Europa shared research portal would allow information sharing including researcher database, publication and dissemination of research results and sharing of research data. This could be used internally or publicly available to give visibility to the alliance and enable Una Europa to better serve society as a whole.
- Funding
 - Practices to access to European funding (MSCA, Horizon Europe)
 - Seed funding initiatives

- Research careers and mobility
 - There were concerns about joint research and PhD positions due to difficulties to align the local recruitment rules. However, creating mobility options like Una Europa chair, Una Europa sabbatical was commonly agreed as preferable practices.
 - Una Europa can also increase attractiveness of individual universities, e.g. by organizing shared recruiting events etc.
 - Una Europa universities research professionals could also visit Una Europa vzw.
- International academic incubators in focus areas continue to promise a pathway approach for a long time to come.
- Support for young researchers:
 - Una Europa joint degrees (BA, MA and PhD) will be known as a quality label for interdisciplinarity
 - Mobility options for Una Europa PhD students and postdoctoral researchers.
 - Early career researchers should develop a sense of belonging to their home institution and the alliance.
- Practices should be developed to receive access to associated (non-academic) partners of the Una Europa universities.
- Una Europa could start research groups on European level as a way to achieve size and capacity to develop more ambitious projects and be successful in competitive calls for research funding.

6. Future UniLab

Future UniLab serves as Una Europa’s think tank. Designed as a ‘living laboratory’, it aims to:

1. Provide a forum for discussion on the future role of universities in society
2. Develop ground-breaking tools and models for cooperation in European Higher Education
3. Assess and future proof Una Europa’s activities.

Una.Resin WP1 follows close the work of the Una Europa Future Uni Lab. In the next stages of the project, WP1 is going to involve the Future UniLab visionaries into the R&I strategy work.

In June 2021, Future UniLab released its first position papers outlining a vision for the European University of the Future. Paper I “Instruments Cluster Envisioning Report” focuses mostly on students and teaching but also entails thoughts for research. The paper envisions the university to be “platforms for personal growth and platforms to change the world.” This corresponds to Una.Resin’s problem-directed focus areas as well as the focus on research careers and human capital development (WP 3). The paper furthermore stresses “openness, transparency, diversity, inclusiveness, fairness, privacy and dignity” as important values that guide a university with porous boundaries. Digital infrastructures should be both developed and used in a collaborative way across institutions and will allow “global networks of researchers can also draw on communities, citizen scientists, gamers, parents, children, prospective students and past alumni to achieve large and rich research samples that would be prohibitive to create from scratch.”

The “Integration Visionaries Team Report” focused on the “unfinishedness” which should be part of university design. HEI should be “open, porous, and contingent to work with others.” These values will be reflected via the cross-cutting theme of open science and citizen engagement. The “Sustainability Cluster”: “Purpose-oriented’ and ‘mission-oriented’ approaches, policies and strategies, should be at the core of future universities, encouraging innovative resource-management models that allow a combination of activities and shared responsibilities.”

Fig. 2: Concept from the Future UniLab Sustainability Cluster – Envisioning Report

7. Conclusion

In the following, we summarize the key outcomes of the benchmarking exercise as well as the community consultations presented in this report. The most important insights were provided by the Una Europa community of researchers and research professionals rather than the strategy benchmarking exercise—an outcome that should be considered in future Una Europa strategy processes. On the other hand, demands and suggestions of the researchers largely matched Una.Resin goals formulated in the GA.

In preparing the Una Europa R&I strategy, the outcomes of these exercises described here will be brought in conversation with relevant European initiatives and strategies: the EC strategy for universities, the European Research Area, the Global Approach to Research and Innovation (R&I), EC Strategic foresight reports and EC Comprehensive Strategy with Africa. We will also align the recommendations and actions developed in Una.Resin with the results and learnings from following activities: the Una Europa 1Europe project, the “Una Europa – Building the European University of the Future” project aims (proposal submitted 22nd March 2022), Una Europa seed funding, Future UniLab position papers, strategies and futures work of the Una Europa self-steering committees and clusters, as well as other Una Europa strategies, in particular Una Europa 2030 strategy and the Una Europa Missions Statement on Africa collaboration.

Connecting People

Researchers welcome the opportunity to collaborate within the Una Europa network. Connecting people should be at the core of Una Europa. Una Europa research collaboration should have a specific focus on early-career researchers and develop fair career assessments that take into account the special nature of multidisciplinary research. Mobility for researchers of all career stages, PhD students as well as professional staff should be possible with minimal bureaucratic efforts.

Researchers desire an online research portal, which allows them to connect with colleagues from different fields and institutes and jointly elaborate on research questions, identify joint research project, and facilitate joint grant proposals, in particular to Horizon Europe calls. The platform could also serve other Una Europa initiatives, such as collecting expressions of interest for seed funding calls. It could be used internally or be openly accessible to give visibility to the alliance and promote open research. Data management and data sharing is a key enabler of joint research and, vice versa, obstacles to sharing form a major barrier for collaboration. The platform could be used as research portal to share research data and publications. Another tool to connect researchers could be a regular UnaFair at which researchers present their work in challenge-based terms and connect with researchers working on the same problem but from a different angle.

Future Priority Areas

The benchmarking did not provide a conclusive picture which research areas or fields lend themselves as new research focus areas for Una Europa. Yet, while the current Una Europa focus areas have been originally chosen to develop teaching collaborations, they also came to serve as incubators for joint research and mostly reflect both strategic choices and areas of research strengths of the partner universities. Una Europa needs to further develop these areas and ensure the participation of relevant stakeholders. Furthermore, Una Europa needs to devise a process to select future focus areas. In addition, Una Europa needs to create structures to support bottom-up research initiatives as well as shared principles how to prioritize them according to the capacities of research support resources.

While researchers are often ahead of institutional futures work and emerging research themes often link to solving societal challenges, research cultures do not support collecting signals. Una Europa could create practices to collect these signals bottom-up and also advice EC futures work and future priorities.

Multidisciplinarity

Multi- and interdisciplinary research is a strategic aim of all Una Europa universities. It was also suggested by researchers as the realm in which Una Europa could be most effective. Multidisciplinary research is regarded

as a way to increase excellence and crucial for solving grand challenges. Besides the existing focus areas, we identified certain areas such as cognitive science and urban studies, where most Una Europa partners possess multidisciplinary structures that could be leveraged towards new Una Europa research collaborations. Several universities maintain institutes that are already focused on interdisciplinary research. Their expertise should be utilized in future Una Europa work. Connecting existing multidisciplinary structures and initiatives can facilitate collaboration across focus areas and inspire bottom-up creation of new research questions. As Una Europa research collaboration is dynamically developing, this should ideally be a continuous process.

Supporting the Future of Una Europa

Researchers regarded the possibility to build deep long-term collaborations as a major added value of Una Europa. While seed funding is an effective incentive to strengthen research collaboration, funding, the procurement of resources and time, as well as effective project management tools are essential to effective long-term collaboration. A major problem that needs to be solved is the lack of support resources in the areas of data sharing and data management. Researchers also called for more legal advice on collaboration with academic and non-academic partners.

Furthermore, to ensure sustainable joint research, collaboration and commonly agreed principles and capacities on management level are pivotal. This capacity should be resourced sufficiently, both at Una Europa vzw and at university level. The current projects (Una.Resin and 1Europe) are targeted at the development of practices but their implementation requires long-term support. The Una Europa universities should agree on funding long-term administrative resources at each university that support Una Europa. It is crucial to identify responsible professionals at each university who coordinate Una Europa projects, support bottom-initiatives and maintain an overview of all Una Europa activities. This will also ensure that academics can easily identify relevant Una Europa points of contact. Rather than creating rigid structures and traditional linear processes, Una Europa should implement organic organisation development that provides for institutional learning and swift adjustment of practices.

Una Europa in the World

Una Europa develops collaboration globally and particularly with universities in the Global South (Una Europa Missions Statement on Africa collaboration). Una Europa could also develop opportunities to host academics at risk by share information about employment opportunities among partners, fund dedicated chairs, doctoral scholarships, and training to enable European integration.

Una Europa should invest in networks with non-academic partners, companies, and other actors, and create novel ways to engage with citizens, for example by developing a partnership programme with clear objectives for teaching and learning as well as research collaboration. The joint ecosystem should be based on Una Europa's shared challenge-based research focus areas. Rather than an abstract entity, the ecosystem should be considered as a network of meaningful connections.

Annex A: Benchmarking Questionnaire

Template Version 9.0 WP1 and WP2 19th May 2021

Context

1.1. Introduction

Una Europa is an alliance of eight leading research universities with global reputation and reach. It is one of 41 emerging European Universities, consisting of bottom-up alliances that aim to create a truly European inter-university environment by triggering unprecedented levels of institutionalised cooperation in the area of education and research. Una Europa has the long-term objective to transform the institutional framework of its member institutions to prepare for the next wave of global challenges.

Through the three-year ERASMUS+ '1Europe' pilot project, Una Europa is taking the first steps towards creating a single education eco-system for our students, by establishing a Europe-wide living lab for testing Joint Innovative Formats for education and mobility, such as joint degrees.

Through the three-year Horizon 2020 'Una.Resin' pilot project, we will determine the purpose for the future research collaboration within and beyond Una Europa. The universities will create strategies for sharing Research & Innovation agendas (WP1), opening up and sharing Research Infrastructure and Resources (WP2), and strengthening Human Capital (WP3). We will implement and evaluate pilot actions for the systematic support for excellence as well as create cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral teams across Una Europa. During the process, we will reach out to the non-academic partners of the universities to strengthen the Una Europa R&I ecosystem as a whole.

More information can be found at the website of Una.Resin: <https://www.una-europa.eu/about/una.resin>.

1.2. Common methodology for Una.Resin Work packages

In order to achieve the objectives of each work package, the Una.Resin projects follows a **common methodology** across work packages:

- Development of shared strategies, agendas and policies following definition of scope, mapping of policies and assets, stakeholder consultation and identification of barriers and enablers of R&I cooperation
- Development of an action plan to implement shared priorities
- Initial implementation via pilot actions
- Evaluation of pilot actions

The common strategy will build on the learnings from the five focus areas, closely linked to Europe's strategic goals: Cultural Heritage; Data Science & Artificial Intelligence; European Studies; Sustainability; and One Health.

The **current focus is on phase 1**, mapping and understanding the relevant policies of the different institutions, providing us with essential information to develop shared strategies. The main methods used in phase 1 are:

1. questionnaires (targeted at policy makers, research administration professionals and relevant academics);
2. co-creation workshops for the academic community (targeted mainly at the academic leaders and other researchers in the five aforementioned Una Europa priority research areas).
3. Guidelines and instructions for completing the benchmarking template

In this first phase we aim to understand and benchmark the existing Research & Innovation and Research Infrastructures & Resources strategies and initiatives of the eight Una Europa universities to identify the complementary strengths of the Una Europa community. We also aim to identify national and organizational policies and mechanisms.

This benchmarking template consists of two questionnaires:

1. Research & Innovation (R&I) strategies and strategic initiatives
2. Research infrastructures and resources (RIRs)

The questionnaires are targeted at the research service professionals at each of the eight Una Europa universities. We encourage to answer the questions together with a team of relevant colleagues and experts in your university.

Guidelines for answering the questions:

1. Please complete the questionnaires by **June 30, 2021 and return your response to WP Leads (1) Elina Tonteri: Una.Resin-UH@helsinki.fi** and (2) Alessia Franchini: a.franchini@unibo.it.
2. Please fill in the name of the university, the name, role and email address of the main contact person, as well as the name, role and e-mail addresses of the main respondents that assisted in completing the different sections of the questionnaire¹;
3. Please use the template questionnaire for answering each item;
4. Please summarize your responses as clearly as possible from the internal consultation.
5. Please limit your answers to the maximum number of words as indicated in the questionnaire (range of 150-250 words);
6. If possible, please provide a link to online materials whenever relevant. If online links are not available, please list the relevant documents in your answer and attach them to the email together with the questionnaire. When doing so, please use the following format:
 - a. Name of the relevant document
 - b. Short description of the document
 - c. Link or name of the attachment

The collected information and materials will be saved on the Una.Resin SharePoint with access limited to the Una.Resin Project office and WP leads and co-leads. These procedures will follow the ethics and security guidelines at the EU level strictly protecting personal and confidential information.

If you have any questions regarding the questionnaires during the data collection, please contact the WP leads* and/or co-leads via email:

Questionnaire part 1: R&I strategies and strategic initiatives (WP1)

- *Elina Tonteri: elina.n.tonteri@helsinki.fi
- Victoria Abakumovskikh: victoria.abakumovskikh@fu-berlin.de

Questionnaire part 2: Research infrastructure and resources (RIRs) (WP2)

- *Alessia Franchini a.franchini@unibo.it
- Hideko Matsuo: Hideko.Matsuo@kuleuven.be
- Veerle Bruggeman: veerle.bruggeman@kuleuven.be
- Wannes Ribbens: Wannes.Ribbens@kuleuven.be

Part 1: R&I Strategies and Strategic Initiatives (WP1)

Administrative information

1. UNIVERSITY:
2. Institutional contact person and email:

Name	Email	Function / Role	Work unit

3. Information on respondents who assisted in completing the questionnaire on joint research and innovation agendas (add more rows if needed):

Name	Email	Function / Role	Work unit

The answers to this part of the benchmarking template will be used for benchmarking the R&I strategies of the Una Europa universities. This is a necessary starting point for building a common Una Europa R&I strategy: where can we be stronger together? As the strategy also reaches beyond the Una Universities to the ecosystem of the community, some questions address the collaborations of the universities with non-academic sectors. Also, to understand the operational environment of our network, some of the questions aim to enlighten the characteristic of the local research cultures and policies.

1. Does your university have a multi annual R&I strategy at university level or is your university planning to adopt such strategies? The strategy may be targeted to defining the direction of research, R&I policies or be a wider university level strategy defining the aims, values or policies of the university.

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please describe (describe in maximum 250 words).
- Provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

2. Has your university defined university level strategic research themes or areas / thematic priorities?

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please list the strategic research themes or areas / thematic priorities and describe them (describe in maximum 250 words). Please indicate if the priority areas listed are university level or tied to a faculty or an institute.
- Please describe the process (if any) at your university for defining the strategic themes or areas (describe in maximum 250 words).
- Does the university provide targeted funding to develop the strategic research themes / priority areas of the university? Please describe (describe in maximum 250 words).
- Provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

3. Are there national or regional policies or funding in place which direct the strategic choices of your university?

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please provide a concise description of relevant policies (describe in maximum 250 words).
- Provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

4. Please list 5-10 top research fields of excellence at your university. Describe the criteria, how these were selected (for example publications, collaborations or other criteria) (describe in maximum 250 words).

5. Are there multidisciplinary structures (institutes, centres etc.) at your university or plans to create such new or additional structures in coming years?

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please list and describe the most relevant existing ones (describe in maximum 250 words).
- If there are plans to create such new or additional structures in coming years please list and describe them (describe in maximum 150 words).
- How does the role of the multidisciplinary structures intersect with traditional faculties and departments (describe in maximum 150 words)?

6. Are there strategies or practices in place that aims at enhancing multidisciplinary research?

Yes

No

If yes:

- What kind of practices have been identified as necessary? What initiatives and instruments are in place to reach this goal? Please describe (describe in maximum 250 words).

7. Please list the most important strategic (top-down) partners or partnerships of your university (other universities, research institutes, cities, museums, companies)? Name up to 15 partners/partnerships.

Name of the partner/partnership	Short description	Link to the Internet site of the partner/partnership

- What are the aims of these partnerships? Please describe (describe in maximum 250 words).
- What kind of binding links do you have with these entities (e.g., memorandum of understanding, cooperation agreements etc.)? Please describe (describe in maximum 250 words).

8. Are there any strategies in place or currently developed that have a dedicated geographical focus, for example, areas of the Global South?

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please list and describe the partnerships (describe in maximum 250 words).
- Provide the relevant link(s) or document(s) if available.

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

9. Does your university have existing pilots, initiatives or strategic partnerships on R&I or research support development with any of the other Una Europa universities?

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please list and the describe briefly the aim and/or field of the partnership.

Partner universities	Name of the collaboration	Short description

10. Does your university have a research code of conduct or comparable value-based regulations for research?

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please describe (describe in maximum 250 words).
- Provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

Part 2: Research Infrastructure and Resources (RIRs) (WP2)

In this first phase we **aim to understand and benchmark the existing strategies, policies and initiatives on research infrastructures and resources (RIRs)** of the eight Una Europa universities in order to identify the complementary strengths, opportunities and barriers for opening-up or sharing research infrastructures and resources. This questionnaire is a pivotal starting point for our common strategy work and the outcomes will be used throughout our three-year project.

The questionnaire has following **three objectives**:

1. To understand the national and regional policies that impact the institutional frameworks on RIRs.
2. To map and understand the policies, funding mechanisms and organisational models/management of RIRs at the different institutions.
3. To form an initial idea about the complementary strengths but also the possible barriers for opening or sharing RIRs.

For this benchmarking exercise, we **start from the European Commission’s definition of Research Infrastructures and Resources:**²

“facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation” including major scientific equipment or sets of instruments, collections, repositories, archives or scientific data, computing systems and communication networks.’

Please refer to the website of the EC for more information (https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/european-research-infrastructures_en)

The thematic focus and delineation of the research infrastructure of interest will be refined with input from the Self-steering Committees / researchers, the cluster on RIRs and other stakeholders at a further stage during the Una.Resin project.

Administrative information

- A. **UNIVERSITY:**
- B. **Institutional contact person and email:**

Name	Email	Function / Role	Work unit

- C. **Information on respondents who assisted in completing the questionnaire on RIRs (add more rows if needed):**

Name	Email	Function / Role	Work unit

Section 1: RIR policy and strategic initiatives at the (inter)national level

International level

1. Does your country/region have a national/regional European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure (ESFRI-oriented)/local roadmap or policy for participation at international infrastructure initiatives? This includes both European and non-European ones.

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please describe in what way universities in your country are involved in the prioritisation and design of this national/regional roadmap (in maximum 250 words).

If yes, provide the relevant link(s) on roadmap and/or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

2. What are the major constraints or difficulties for your institution to participate in large European infrastructure initiatives?³ Multiple responses are possible and please describe this for each relevant item.

financial aspects (describe in maximum 150 words)

human resources (describe in maximum 150 words)

legal aspects concerning access of the infrastructure (describe in maximum 150 words)

data sharing (describe in maximum 150 words)

IP of data (describe in maximum 150 words)

physical distance (describe in maximum 150 words)

others than above (describe in maximum 150 words)

3. Is the participation of academic research groups at large European infrastructure initiatives financed at the national/regional level?

Yes

No

If yes, please explain in maximum 250 words.

National level

4. Are there specific programmes at the national/regional level (e.g., by government, funding agencies) which fund RIRs for universities and research institutions?

Yes

No

If yes:

- Please describe in maximum 250 words which type of RIRs and budget limits can be applied for?
- Please stipulate the general policy – if any – funders have on the sharing of those infrastructure? (Describe in maximum in 250 words)
- Please provide links to the website and documentation wherever possible.

If yes, provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

If yes:

- Is the national/regional definition of RIRs aligned with the definition of EC⁴?

Yes

No

If no, what is the difference (maximum 150 words)?

5. Does your country have funding mechanisms to support national/regional RIR infrastructure which is used for Open Science purposes?

Yes

No

6. Does your institution have access to national/regional RIR infrastructure which is used for Open Science purposes?

Yes

No

7. If yes in item 6, which ones (multiple choices are possible), and please include a short description if necessary, and relevant websites and documents where relevant.

- publication repository (describe in maximum 150 words)
- publication platform (describe in maximum 150 words)
- data repository (describe in maximum 150 words)
- data management infrastructure and tools (describe in maximum 150 words)
- data sharing infrastructure (describe in maximum 150 words)
- Other (describe in maximum 150 words)

If **yes**, provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

8. If yes in item 6: is access for researchers from other countries regulated?

- Yes
- No

If **yes**, please describe how access is regulated. Please include a short description and relevant websites and documents where necessary.

- publication repository (describe in maximum 150 words)
- publication platform (describe in maximum 150 words)
- data repository (describe in maximum 150 words describe)
- data management infrastructure and tools (describe in maximum 150 words describe)
- data sharing infrastructure (describe in maximum 150 words describe)
- Other (describe in maximum 150 words describe)

If **yes**, provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

Section 2: RIR policies and organization at the university level

9. Does your university have a common centralized university policy/strategy on RIRs?

Yes

No

If yes: what are the most important aspects of this policy? Please describe in maximum 250 words and give, if possible, a website link or provide the documentation.

If no: please explain in maximum 250 words, why there is not (yet) a university-wide policy from your point of view?

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

10. Are there general policies on RIRs in departments, faculties, institutes, research units that differ from the university-wide (centralized) policy?

Yes

No

If yes, what are the most important aspects of these policies? Please describe in maximum 250 words.

11. Please describe in maximum 250 words the responsibilities on RIRs (purchase, use, maintenance, upgrade, personnel, ...) of the different levels within the university (e.g., central administration, departments/faculties, research groups, researcher)?

12. To what extent, and how are the decentralized policies in departments, faculties, institutes, research units complementary to the central university policy? Please describe in maximum 250 words.

13. Do these policies on RIRs take Open Science principles into consideration?

Yes

No

If yes, please explain in maximum 250 words.

14. Does your university have policies and/or best practices for sharing RIRs?

Yes

No

If yes,

(policies)

- For which research infrastructures?
- Are you already sharing infrastructure with other universities or non-academic parties (e.g., use, management, funding, operational capacity, ...), inside or outside your country?

Yes

No

If yes, which infrastructures and how (maximum 150 words)?

(best practice)

- For which research infrastructures?
- Do these best practices involve other universities or non-academic parties (e.g., use, management, funding, operational capacity, ...), inside or outside your country?

If yes, which infrastructures and how (describe in maximum 150 words)?

15. What are the major sources of financing RIRs at your university? Please specify between the international/regional/national/university levels and **also please give the estimation by % proportions if possible.**

- International (describe in maximum 150 words)
- Regional (describe in maximum 150 words)
- National (describe in maximum 150 words)
- University (describe in maximum 150 words)

16. If there are (university) budgets for RIRs, what do they support (e.g., budget for new equipment, data storage, personnel supporting infrastructure, user fees....)? Please describe these different aspects in maximum 250 words.

17. Do you have any RIRs that are already part of a European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure (ERIC) or other EU funded infrastructure (INFRA) project?

Yes

No

If yes, please, provide the list (and related links).

Name infrastructure	Link	Open for Trans National Access / researchers from other countries (yes / no)

18. Does your university have core facilities⁵ officially recognised by the university?

Yes

No

If yes, please provide the relevant link(s) and/or document(s)?

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

If yes, can you also describe in general the following aspects of core facilities?

organisation and management (e.g., steering and other committees, presence of core facility coordinator, technical staff, ...) (describe in maximum 150 words)

access (website, reservations, ...) (describe in maximum 150 words)

users: type of users (internal, external (international, industry, ...), user fees, training of users, type of service (academic, by contract, ...)) (describe in maximum 150 words)

long-term planning (financing of personnel, new investments, ...) (describe in maximum 150 words)

19. Do you have training activities (tutorials, training modules, etc.) for the use of specific RIRs?

Yes

No

If yes, please describe in maximum 150 words.

20. Do you have a centralised (e.g., single document or a website) catalogue for (a part of) your university RIRs?

Yes

No

If yes, provide the relevant link(s) or document(s).

Title document	Short description	Link or name of attachment

If yes, who (which unit) is responsible for submitting and updating the information in this catalogue?

21. Do you have a communication strategy to inform academic and/or non-academic stakeholders about the opportunity to use RIRs?

Yes

No

If yes, please describe the communication strategy (target group(s), who is responsible for this strategy (university level, departments/faculties, ...), ...) in maximum 250 words?

22. Does your university have a research data storage⁶ policy?

Yes

No

If yes, please describe in maximum 250 words how research data storage is organized and managed within your university? Please also include description if research groups manage this differently.

Central storage facilities (describe in maximum 250 words)

Distributed storage facilities (describe in maximum 250 words describe)

Local, in research groups (describe in maximum 250 words describe)

Other, specify: ... (describe in maximum 250 words describe)

23. What are currently the major bottlenecks in maintaining and upgrading RIRs at your university? Multiple choices are possible and please describe each relevant bottleneck.

Lack of budget (specify) (describe in maximum 150 words)

Infrastructure experts (describe in maximum 150 words)

Coordination of facilities (describe in maximum 150 words)

Others (describe in maximum 150 words)

24. What are currently the major bottlenecks in sharing RIRs at your university? Please describe in maximum 250 words.

Thank you for taking the time to answer these questions!

END OF QUESTIONNAIRE

Annex B: Strategies of Una Europa Universities

Freie Universität Berlin (FUB)

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Annex C: Atlas.si Figures

Fig. 1 Intentions: Values. The figure depicts values that underline institutional strategies as well as intentions linked to these values. Also depicted are examples such as initiatives or existing policies. Two sets of values can be distinguished: openness, impact, influence and university ideologies. **Blue boxes** mark intentions described in research strategies or in parts of general strategies concerned with research. **White boxes** depict values expressed in general strategies or value manifestos.

Fig. 2 Intentions: Impact. Targets of impact in the clusters explicate the intentions regarding the respective impact or define further how the respective impact is comprehended. **Blue boxes** are intentions derived from research strategies or those parts of general strategies concerned research. **White boxes** are derived from general strategies.

Fig. 3 Intentions: Internal development. There are three main clusters in the figure: education development, development of research activities, and management & governance development. **Blue boxes** are intentions from research strategies, or those parts of general strategies concerned with research. **White boxes** are derived from general strategies.